

Editorial

The Birth of the Journal of Molecular Pathology

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In the era of personalized/precision medicine, the relevance of molecular pathology cannot be overemphasized. Any improvement in the understanding of disease mechanisms—in their classifications and diagnosis, in the prognostic evaluation and in the predictive workup—is indissolubly related to one of the many facets of molecular pathology. This modern discipline represents, in clinical practice, a key component of the scientific multidisciplinary approach, which faces an increasing number of many different disease types. To fully cover any aspect of modern precision medicine, which is difficult to investigate, a large group of experts representing many different backgrounds has to be built. A journal that has the ambition to convey the most novel and relevant developments of this discipline to the largest possible audience in the molecular pathology community needs to be deeply rooted in strong soil. The Journal of Molecular Pathology (JMP), published by MDPI group, is taking the first steps in the field of diagnostic and predictive assessments of solid tumors. To address these aims and to keep our journal updated, the editorial board is composed of fully qualified morpho-molecular pathologists who have collaborated for many years and are involved in common translational research projects, spanning from benchtop to clinical practice. Since 2010, this close-knit group of researchers have shared the latest research in the field of molecular pathology every year, outlining the research hot topics at the international Molecular Cytopathology Meeting [1,2]. As an example, novel tools useful for the validation of next generation technologies in molecular predictive pathology have been developed by our group of scientists [3,4]. Other collaborations within this worldwide network are ongoing; this is crucial as the development of common projects and reciprocal support is imperative to overcome the difficulties in sharing research data with scientific gatherings in this critical historic moment [5]. With great enthusiasm, the JMP editorial board is currently preparing a first special issue that will review the key aspects of predictive molecular pathology in solid tumors, focusing on knowledge gaps and further developments.

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